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A STUDY OF DIFFERENCES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF TORIA

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Abstract

Difference in 105 genotypes of toria germ plasm was evaluated by statistical methods. Oil content, fatty acid composition and glucosinolate content was estimated and data obtained for various characters were subjected to statistical analysis i.e. analysis of variance, measurement of genetic divergence. Analysis of variance indicated that all the genotypes were significantly different from each other for all the characters. 105 genotypes, included in the study were grouped into 8 clusters. Genotypes occupying one cluster may also have little diversity and selection of parents within the cluster may also be useful. This information on relationship within and between genotypes of the same species will be valuable for organizing germ plasm and selecting parents for breeding purposes.

Key words: *Brassica campestris*, toria, genetic divergence, variability

Introduction

Description of a variety is based upon the traits that reflect genetic variation. It can be used to measure genetic divergence and can, therefore, be used to monitor and promote efficient conservation and utilization of genetic divergence (Cho et al. 1999). Traits used to measure genetic divergence in toria includes oil content, fatty acid profile, glucosinolate content. Estimates of genetic divergence based on these traits have been obtained for several crops by several workers (Yadav et al., 1973; Chaubey and Katiyar, 1979; Verma et al, 2002). Present paper deals with the analysis of genetic divergence in 105 genotypes of *B.campestris*.

Materials and Method

The material for the present study consists of hundred and five genotypes of Toria. These genotypes were grown in the controlled conditions in disease free green house at Botanical Garden, School of Life Sciences, Dr B.R. Ambedkar University, Agra.

15-20 gms of whole seeds of were dried in oven at 100°C for overnight. Samples were removed from oven and let them cool for two hours. Percentage of oil was calculated by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance.

Glucosinolate content was estimated by sodium tetra chloropalladate with the help of ELISA Reader. Seed sample were dried in oven at 70-80°C and crushed with the help of mortar and pastle. Crushed seeds were transferred in the test tube and 300 μ l 70% methanol was added in the sample. Sample tubes were kept immediately into the water bath at 80°C for 5 minutes. 2 ml double distilled boiling water was added and vortexed .Samples were again kept into water bath for 15-20 minutes then allowed to cool at room temperature and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. 5 μ l of the supernatant was taken into the well of a microtitre plate along with standard. 300 μ l of sodium tetrachloropalladate reagent was added. Microtitre plate was put into oven at 70°C for 30 min to form the complex between sample and reagent. Absorption value was taken against blank at 405 nm by ELISA Reader. Then amount of glucosinolate was calculated using following formula-

$$\text{Amount of Glucosinolate} \quad (\mu \text{ mole / gram of fatfree oilcake}) = \frac{\text{Absorption value of unknown}}{\text{Absorption value of known}} \times \frac{\text{known concentration}}{(\mu \text{ mole})}$$

Fatty acid composition of esterified constituents of seed oil was determined by methylating the fatty acyl esters in the oil and then chromatographing these methyl esters on a gas chromatograph. The method of direct methylation of seeds is modification of Hougen and Boda (1973). 8-10 dry seeds were taken into glass tube and 500 μ l petroleum ether was added .After 15 minutes seeds were ground and 1 ml of methylating solution was added. After 45-50 minutes 500 μ l distilled water was added, vortexed at 5000 rpm. 1 μ l sample from upper layer was taken with the help of micro syringe, for fatty acid analysis by Gas Liquid Chromatography.

Data obtained for various characters were subjected to statistical analysis.

The estimation of genetic divergence of 105 genotypes was done following 'Mahalanobis' D² statistic (generalized distance) as suggested by Rao (1952).

Results and Discussion

The genetic improvement of any crop usually involves three main steps viz. (I) creation of variation, (II) selection of superior genotypes and (III) the utilization of selected genotypes to generate a superior variety i.e. evaluation. Among these, the second step is very crucial upon which the success of a plant breeding programme depends. To select desired genotypes in a particular crop species, breeders need basic information on the extent and nature of variability present in the available germ plasm, nature of association among various characters and heritability of the characters under improvement.

Analysis of variance indicated that all the genotypes were significantly different from each other for all the characters (Table-1).

The degree of genetic divergence, which literally means how two or more populations are genetically different from each other, when several characters are taken into account was quantified by Mahalanobis's(1936) and gave the idea of generalized distance (D²) when the effect of environment has been the same.

105 genotypes, included in the study were grouped into 8 clusters. The clustering pattern has been presented in Table-2. 86 genotypes fell in cluster I, 9 in cluster II, 4 in cluster III, 2 in cluster IV, one each in cluster V, VI, VII and VIII. The average intra and inter cluster D² and D values are presented in Tables-

3 and 4, respectively. The maximum average intra cluster D^2 value (9163.92) and maximum average intra cluster distance (95.73) was recorded in cluster IV. Whereas, the minimum average intra cluster D^2 value (2122.33) and minimum average intra cluster distance (46.07) was recorded in cluster I.

Based on D^2 statistic, the biological population has been successfully classified (Majumdar and Rao, 1949; Mukherji, 1951; Nair and Mukherji, 1960; Murty et al., 1962 and Cassie, 1962).

Anand and Rawat (1985) studied clustering pattern in Indian mustard and suggested that selection of parents on the basis of diversity estimates may be useful in a crop breeding programme. Jagdev et al. (1991) studied 19 strains of rapeseed mustard, which were grouped into 5 clusters using D^2 static.

Table-1: Analysis of variance for various characters)

Source of Variation	Degree of freedom	Oil Content	Glucos -inolate	Palmitic Acid	Stearic Acid	Oleic Acid	Linoleic Acid	Linolenic Acid	Eicosenoic Acid	Erucic Acid
Treatment	104	9.87	1001.51	1.46	0.39	31.53	100.34	47.04	22.87	237.88
Error	104	4.98	427.93	0.88	0.18	0.78	0.49	0.17	0.12	5.44
S.Em ²		1.57	14.62	0.21	0.30	0.20	0.50	0.93	0.78	1.65
General Mean		41.87	130.74	2.98	0.50	10.83	17.57	12.78	9.79	44.16
CV(%)		5.33	15.82	9.97	8.46	2.58	4.00	1.03	1.13	5.28
CD(1%)		5.86	54.27	0.78	0.11	0.73	1.85	0.34	0.29	6.12
CD(5%)		4.43	41.01	0.59	0.84	0.55	1.39	0.26	0.22	4.62

Table-2: Clustering pattern of different genotypes

Cluster	Genotypes	Total Number of Genotypes
I	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 46, 47, 48, 52, 53, 55, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102, 103, 105	86
II	7, 11, 18, 19, 45, 49, 50, 54, 57	9
III	56, 63, 64, 97	4
IV	8, 13	2
V	28	1
VI	51	1
VII	89	1
VIII	104	1

Based on the present investigation, it is concluded that the genetic divergence is not related to geographical diversity (Murty and Quadri, 1966; Yadav et al, 1973; Mangath et al., 1974; Dubey, 1976; Fanizza et al., 1992 and Verma et al., 2002). The intra cluster distance varied between 97.73 for cluster

IV to 00.00 for V, VI, VII and VIII clusters. This suggests that genotypes occupying one cluster may also have little diversity and selection of parents within the cluster may also be useful. The inter cluster distance varied between 37.13 in clusters I and V to 196.68 for clusters IV and VII. The minimum distance between clusters suggested a fairly close-relationship of genotypes of these cluster pairs. The relatively less variations among the values for cluster means between these two clusters also confirm the above results. These results indicate that there is no parallelism between geographical and genetic diversity.

It is concluded and suggested that genotypes occupying one group have little diversity and selection of parents between two groups will be very useful. This information on relationship within and between genotypes of the same species will be valuable for organizing germplasm and selecting parents for breeding purposes. These selected and newly developed varieties will be useful for increasing both production and productivity.

Table-3: Average intra diagonal and inter cluster D² values in toria.

Clusters	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
I	<u>2122.73</u>	17293.45	18017.21	28646.69	1378.46	10473.51	8546.45	12951.71
II		<u>2957.05</u>	18349.63	36274.82	19654.42	28713.52	14834.02	23844.36
III			<u>3881.47</u>	10015.44	19588.30	28507.75	24274.75	21181.30
IV				<u>9163.92</u>	28865.98	38612.34	38612.34	18679.22
V					<u>0.00</u>	9931.91	9931.91	11832.25
VI						<u>0.00</u>	15687.77	16589.08
VII							<u>0.00</u>	15829.79
VIII								<u>0.00</u>

Table-4: Average intra (diagonal) and inter cluster D values.

Clusters	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
I	<u>46.07</u>	131.50	134.23	169.25	37.13	102.34	92.45	113.81
II		<u>54.38</u>	135.46	190.46	140.19	169.45	121.79	154.42
III			<u>62.30</u>	100.08	139.96	168.84	155.80	145.54
IV				<u>95.73</u>	169.90	193.94	196.68	136.67
V					<u>0.00</u>	95.84	99.66	108.78
VI						<u>0.00</u>	125.25	128.80
VII							<u>0.00</u>	125.82
VIII								<u>0.00</u>

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